

1 **Adding colour to mass spectra: Charge Determination Analysis (CHARDA) assigns**
2 **charge state to every ion peak**

3

4 Yaroslav Lyutvinskiy,¹ Konstantin O. Nagornov,² Anton N. Kozhinov,² Natalia Gasilova,³
5 Laure Menin,³ Zhaowei Meng,¹ Xuepei Zhang,¹ Amir Ata Saei,^{1,4} Yury O. Tsybin,²
6 Alexander Makarov,⁵ Roman A. Zubarev^{1,6,7*}

7

8 ¹Division of Physiological Chemistry I, Department of Medical Biochemistry and Biophysics,
9 Karolinska Institutet, SE-17 177 Stockholm, Sweden

10 ²Spectroswiss, 1015 Lausanne, Switzerland

11 ³Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, 1015 Lausanne, Switzerland

12 ⁴Department of Cell Biology, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA 02115, USA

13 ⁵ThermoFisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany

14 ⁶SciLifeLab, Stockholm, Sweden

15 ⁷Department of Pharmacological & Technological Chemistry, I.M. Sechenov First Moscow
16 State Medical University, Moscow, Russia

17

18

19

20 *Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to R.A.Z. (email:
21 Roman.Zubarev@ki.se)

22

23 **Abstract**

24 Traditionally, mass spectrometry (MS) output is the ion abundance plotted versus ionic mass-
25 to-charge ratio m/z . While employing only commercially available equipment, Charge
26 Determination Analysis (CHARDA) adds a third dimension to MS, estimating for individual
27 peaks their charge states z , starting from $z=1$, and colour-coding z in m/z spectra. CHARDA
28 combines the analysis of ion signal decay rates in the time-domain data (transients) in Fourier
29 transform (FT) MS with the interrogation of mass defects of biopolymers. Being applied to
30 individual isotopic peaks in a complex protein tandem (MS/MS) dataset, CHARDA
31 facilitates charge state deconvolution of large ionic species in crowded regions, estimating z
32 even in the absence of isotopic distribution (*e.g.*, for monoisotopic mass spectra). CHARDA
33 is fast, robust and consistent with conventional FT MS and FT MS/MS data acquisition
34 procedures. An effective charge state resolution $R_z \geq 6$ is obtained, with potential for further
35 improvements.

36

37

38

39 Introduction

40 Traditionally, mass spectrometry (MS) measures mass-to-charge ratio m/z of ions, providing
41 two-dimensional mass spectra, where the ion abundance is plotted against the ionic m/z . At
42 the same time, the main parameters of interest are the compound's neutral mass m and its
43 abundance. During the first seven decades of MS development, the absolute majority of mass
44 spectra contained only singly charged ions, and with the experimental mass error being much
45 larger than the electron mass, the m/z values were in practice equal to the neutral mass. The
46 situation has changed with the advent of electrospray ionization (ESI) and similar techniques
47 producing multiply-charged ions of polypeptides¹. In response to that, various approaches
48 emerged aimed at estimating m from multi-charge MS data. Up to now, the two main
49 strategies of charge state deconvolution are both based on using several ion peaks originating
50 from the same molecule. In lower-resolution mass spectra of biopolymers, the m/z difference
51 between different charge states is employed². In high-resolution mass spectra, where
52 individual isotopic peaks are resolved, z can be deduced as the closest integer to
53 $(1.003*k)/\Delta m/z$, where $\Delta m/z$ is the distance on the m/z scale between the N -th and $(N+k)$ th
54 peaks in an isotopic cluster, with N being a positive integer. However, in crowded mass
55 spectra the isotopic clusters often overlap, making it difficult to determine which ones of the
56 multitude of closely spaced ion peaks belong to the same isotopic cluster³.

57 To address this issue, several methods have emerged to estimate the charge states of
58 individual ion peaks independently from the other ions in a mass spectrum. Most of these
59 methods are based on measuring the charge of individual ions. An early approach used a
60 secondary ion detector, in which the number of secondary ions created by an incident analyte
61 ion depended upon the ion kinetic energy. As the kinetic energy of an ion accelerated by a
62 potential difference ΔU is $z\Delta U$, the number of secondary ions depends upon the ionic charge
63 z ⁴. Similarly, a time-of-flight cryodetector could measure the kinetic energy of the ions
64 impacting the detector, which correlated with the ionic charge⁵. Charge detection mass
65 spectrometry (CDMS) measures the charge of individual ions by the signal induced by them
66 on an image current detector that records a time-domain signal, or transient. CDMS then
67 applies the Fourier transform (FT) or a similar approach to these time-domain signals to
68 derive z and m/z of ions⁶. The recent technique called individual ion MS (I²MS) implements
69 CDMS in commercially available OrbitrapTM mass spectrometers⁷. In the I²MS approach,
70 ≤ 120 individual ions are obtained per spectrum acquisition, with thousands of acquisitions
71 obtained to generate a full mass spectrum. The ionic charge state is estimated based on the

72 fact that ion peak's abundance increases with time-domain transient duration in a charge-state
73 dependent manner. I²MS can assign the charge state even in the absence of isotopic
74 resolution, which is particularly useful for very large ions, such as protein complexes. On the
75 other hand, many thousands of acquisitions may be required to generate the charge
76 calibration curve by the I²MS approach, and it is limited by the lowest charge state $z \approx 10$.
77 Increasing time-domain transient duration in I²MS may help to improve the charge state limit
78 of detection, albeit at the expense of a proportionally increased experimental time. In
79 measuring $z=22+$ ions, Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) charge state resolving power
80 $R_z \approx 2$ has been obtained ⁷, with higher charge resolution for higher charge states.

81 Here we present the Charge Determination Analysis (CHARDA) method that is
82 applicable in FT MS for all charge states starting from $z=1$. In CHARDA, a calibration curve
83 can be obtained from a single mass spectrum acquired with commercially available FTMS
84 equipment in a conventional data acquisition mode, allowing for post-processing already
85 acquired MS and MS/MS data. While not requiring single ion detection, or detection of very
86 small number of ions per mass spectrum, CHARDA still adds a third dimension to MS by
87 estimating the charge state z for every ion peak in the FT mass spectrum. For compact
88 representation of 3D information, the ion charge state is displayed by colour-coding the ion
89 peaks.

90 **Method**

91 CHARDA combines the complementary approaches of time-domain transient decay
92 analysis (TDA) characteristic for FTMS with mass defect interrogation (MDI) that can be
93 implemented using any high-resolution mass spectra (Figure 1). TDA utilizes the well-known
94 fact that in FTMS, the time-domain transient, theoretically being nearly sinusoidal, is actually
95 more complex, often close to a sinusoidal wave with exponentially decaying amplitude
96 (Figure 1, upper left). The decay is usually attributed to collisions with the residual gas ⁸. The
97 exponent parameter known as decay constant $1/\tau$ is thus linked to the collisional cross section
98 (CCS) ⁹. For ions with a similar m/z , larger mass (and thus also larger charge) tends to imply
99 larger CCS, and thus faster transient decay. Indeed, the ions in the m/z interval 772-780 have
100 the following experimental CCS values: ubiquitin 11+ (8.6 kDa) - 2394 Å², whereas
101 apomyoblobyn 22+ (17.0 kDa) - 4887 Å² ¹⁰. In ion mobility MS, very similar CCS values
102 (2340 and 4920 Å², respectively) have been obtained for these ions ¹¹. Thus we concluded
103 that decay constants in FTMS must carry charge-predictive information. Indeed, using the

104 linear regression of the above values for 11+ ubiquitin and 22+ apomyoblobin, the cross
105 section of 3528 \AA^2 corresponds to the charge state $z=16.004\pm0.010$, a very accurate estimate
106 for the 16+ cytochrome C ions with such an experimental CCS value determined by FTMS ¹⁰.

107 Note that the charge state being a discrete value, the accuracy of its estimation in the
108 above example is greatly excessive. Monte Carlo simulations showed that, as long as the
109 standard deviation of both calibration CCSs is kept below 2.4%, more than 95% of the charge
110 state estimates approximated to the nearest integer were correct, i.e. 16+. With a $\leq 6.7\%$
111 standard deviation, $>95\%$ cases gave the correct charge state within a ± 1 charge state margin,
112 and with a $\leq 10.6\%$ standard deviation - within ± 2 charge state units. Even such approximate
113 charge state assignment can be useful in practice.

114 In TDA, the transient is first converted using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to a
115 frequency domain spectrum, and the latter – to an m/z spectrum (Figure 1, 1). The ion peaks
116 are distinguished from the background by an appropriate algorithm. Narrow m/z areas around
117 every individual peak are then converted to a time-domain partial transient using inverse FFT,
118 and the decay parameter of this partial transient is estimated. There are several known ways
119 to estimate the decay constant $1/\tau$, including STORI plots ¹² and FIR filtering ¹³, but we have
120 found experimentally that fitting a decaying exponent $\exp(-t/\tau)$ to the time interval of 0.2-1.0
121 s (more general, from 1/8 to 5/8 of the transient) provides the best charge resolution.

122 In parallel, FFT of the two halves of the full transient, A and B, is performed, each
123 half-transient providing an ion peak at the same position as with full transient but at half the
124 m/z resolution. The ratio of the intensities of the peak in FFT(B) versus FFT(A), $\eta = \frac{FFT(B)}{FFT(A)}$
125 (Figure 1, 3), the decay constant $1/\tau$, the peak m/z and abundances are then combined in a
126 single z -predictive TDA model.

127 This model is calibrated as follows. First, a conventional algorithm of charge state
128 deconvolution based on the isotopic distribution of ions is applied to the whole m/z spectrum,
129 generating a list of identified isotopic clusters with reliably determined charge states. These
130 usually encompass $<10\%$ of the ion peaks in a mass spectrum. Then a logistic regression
131 model is built based on these reliably identified charge states predicting z from the transient
132 parameters for any ion peak.

133 The position of ions on the m/z scale also carries information of the molecular mass,
134 and thus about the charge state of ions z . A large fraction of all FTMS analyses performed to

135 date concerns polypeptides, and thus our discussion will be limited to these biopolymers. The
136 mass defect interrogation (MDI) investigates the ionic mass defect d_m , which is defined here
137 as a difference between the accurate neutral mass of a compound and its nearest lower-mass
138 integer approximation: *e.g.*, mass defect of $m=2083.8753$ Da is $d_m=0.8753$ Da. For
139 monoisotopic polypeptide molecular masses, mass defect is a periodic function with a period
140 of 1.9-2.2 kDa ¹⁴⁻¹⁷. MDI uses the well-known fact that the monoisotopic molecular mass
141 defects are not evenly distributed over the mass scale but are clustered around their average
142 values ¹⁴. For instance, for the monoisotopic polypeptide masses between 1000 and 1001 Da,
143 the mass defect distribution is centered around 0.55 Da, with a majority of molecules falling
144 within the ± 0.1 Da interval around this value ¹⁶. For other isotopic peaks of proteins, mass
145 defects increase by ≈ 3 mDa for every Dalton away from the monoisotopic peak. This is
146 because ¹³C is the main contributor to the isotopic distribution, with the mass difference
147 between ¹³C and ¹²C of ≈ 1.0033 Da, while the presence of other elements makes the average
148 inter-isotope distance in polypeptides closer to 1.003 Da.

149 Since the difference between the average isotopic mass and monoisotopic one
150 increases by 1 Da for every 1.6-1.8 kDa of molecular mass increase ¹⁴, and the mass of the
151 most abundant isotopologue is always ≤ 1 Da below the average isotopic mass ¹⁸, for
152 polypeptides below 25 kDa the most abundant isotopologue has a mass defect within 0.05 Da
153 of the monoisotopic mass defect (disregarding the discontinuity occurring when d_m reaches
154 1.0). Therefore, knowing the theoretical distribution of mass defects as a function of
155 polypeptide mass, one can obtain a probability estimate for different charge states of that
156 mass. As an example, for a polypeptide ion with m/z 1000.200, the charge state 1+ is highly
157 unlikely, as the mass defect of 200 mDa falls within the forbidden “band gap” between the
158 mass distribution peaks. According to Mann ¹⁵, the molecular mass at which the interval
159 encompassing $\geq 95\%$ of all amino acid compositions exceeds 1 Da is ≈ 8 kDa. Thus around
160 and beyond that critical mass the band gap disappears and the distribution of monoisotopic
161 protein masses becomes pseudo-continuous (there are still gaps on a micro-scale). However,
162 the differences between the regular maxima and minima of the distribution remain significant
163 for much larger masses, and thus MDI analysis is still plausible.

164 Molecular mass defects have previously been used to estimate the probability of a
165 given mass to belong to a peptide ¹⁹ or to a modified peptide ²⁰. But the use of d_m to augment
166 charge state determination in polypeptides appears to be novel ²¹, while the link between the
167 mass defect and the charge state for synthetic polymers has recently been explored ²². In our

168 implementation MDI uses not only monoisotopic molecular masses, but also poly-isotopic
169 masses as charge state is predicted for any ion peak regardless of its position in the isotopic
170 cluster.

171 When CHARDA is applied to an individual m/z peak resolved in a mass spectrum
172 (Figure 1, 4), both the TDA model and the MDI model predict the ion's charge state and its
173 probability density distribution (Figure 1, 5-6). The MDI model is universal and only needs
174 to be adjusted if a different class of molecules than unmodified polypeptides is considered
175 (e.g., specifically modified polypeptides, polymers, RNAs, sugars, etc.). To create such a
176 model from scratch, theoretical mass distribution needs to be simulated for a given class of
177 molecules, including not only monoisotopic masses but also those of other isotopologues.
178 The discrete nature of this distribution²³ can cause inconveniences, and thus the distribution
179 has to be averaged with a narrow window (e.g., 0.01 Da), providing smooth periodic
180 envelopes. The envelopes have distinct peaks at low molecular masses with "band gaps"
181 between them. The abundance of a peak at each mass unit is normalized, so that its area is
182 unity. Such normalization converts the mass distribution into a mass-dependent probability
183 distribution function. The probability of a certain discrete z for a specific m/z value is
184 established assuming that the ionic charge is due to protonation. Therefore, the value of $(m/z -$
185 $m_p) \cdot z$ with its error band ($m_p=1.007277$ is proton's m/z) is mapped onto the probability
186 distribution, and the area under the curve (AUC) is established. In a similar manner, AUCs
187 are obtained for other plausible z values, and all thus obtained AUCs are normalized such that
188 their sum is unity. In the MDI model, thus normalized AUCs represent the probabilities for a
189 given m/z to correspond to respective z values.

190 The TDA and MDI probability charge state density distributions for a given ion peak are
191 merged, giving rise to a single distribution (Figure 1, 7). The most probable charge state
192 value (not necessarily an integer) as well as the interval of charge state values corresponding
193 to >95% certainty ($p<0.05$) are thus determined. This charge state value is then colour-coded
194 into the ion peak envelope in the mass spectrum, providing a third dimension of information
195 (Figure 1, 8).

196 RESULTS

197 Proof of principle

198 As a proof of principle, we analyzed an MS/MS spectrum of ubiquitin 11+ ions acquired on
199 a Q Exactive HF Orbitrap (Thermo) as a sum of 350 individual transients, each 1.5 s duration

200 ²⁴. The mass spectrum contains 33,796 ion peaks, of which 7208 peaks (21 % of the total)
201 representing 2323 isotopic clusters were charge-state deconvolved using the Hardklör
202 algorithm ²⁵. In total 1167 peaks in 212 clusters were recognized as being due to ubiquitin b/y
203 product ions, and 533 most reliable of them (see Methods section) representing 159 isotopic
204 clusters with z ranging from 1+ to 9+ were used for the TDA model calibration. Figure 2a
205 demonstrates that the TDA-extracted decay constants scale linearly with the monoisotopic
206 molecular mass of the calibration ions. Figure 2b shows the distribution of the CHARDA-
207 predicted charge states of these peaks and their Gaussian fits versus the charge state
208 determined by the Hardklör algorithm.

209 In order to optimize the CHARDA algorithm, a quantitative measure of its performance
210 was needed. Such a measure was charge state resolution determined as the maximum value of
211 the predicted charge state divided by FWHM of the fitted bell curves as in Figure 2b
212 averaged over all charge states. The thus determined TDA resolution was 5.6, while the
213 addition of MDI improved the resolution to 6.0 (Figure S1). As expected, most of the
214 improvements were observed for the lower charge states, starting from $z=1$.

215 Figure 3a shows the application of CHARDA to a busy region of the MS/MS spectrum
216 between m/z 811.0 and 813.5. The colour-coded peaks allow one to easily discern separate
217 isotopic clusters. To reduce the complexity, the spectrum can be divided into three subspectra
218 of overlapping charge state intervals, e.g. $z \leq 4$, $3 \leq z \leq 6$ and $z \geq 5$ (Figure 3b-d).

219 Hardklör deconvolution of the whole MS/MS spectrum presented in an expanded view in
220 Figure 3 gave 212 isotopic clusters. To estimate the effect of CHARDA on isotopic
221 deconvolution, the entire MS/MS spectrum was divided into eight subspectra, one for every
222 predicted charge state, with peaks having a >1% probability to be in a given charge state
223 included in the corresponding subspectrum. In each subspectrum, Hardklör deconvolved the
224 isotopic clusters, producing additional 19 isotopic clusters (a 9% improvement) that were
225 missed in the full-spectrum deconvolution. The masses of all these clusters corresponded to
226 expected fragment ions of ubiquitin. This result confirms that CHARDA can improve
227 isotopic cluster deconvolution for busy tandem mass spectra.

228

229 **Manual spectra inspection**

230 Another possible CHARDA application is the manual inspection of mass spectra with
231 overlapping charge state distributions of molecular or fragment ions. This is particularly
232 useful when proteins exist in different proteoforms ²⁶, and thus there is no clear “charge state
233 ladder” in a mass spectra. As an example, Figure 4a shows a colour-coded mass spectrum

234 with a 1 s transient duration of a mixture of three proteins. Colour-coding was made by TDA
235 without accurate calibration of charge states, by instructing the algorithm to recognize
236 different charge states using the maximum likelihood approach. For clarity the charge state
237 ladders are connected by lines. While many peaks obviously do not belong to any ladder,
238 their tentative attribution to this or that protein molecule can be facilitated by peak colour
239 coding. This attribution can be verified by other approaches, such as charge state
240 deconvolution by Hardklör or MS/MS.

241

242 **Absence of isotopic resolution**

243 In the absence of isotopic resolution, the ion peak represents a weighted average of the whole
244 isotopic envelope. We performed numerous CHARDA on a transient shortened from to 0.5 s
245 that gave isotopic distributions merged into a single peak, but were unable to predict charge
246 states correctly at such conditions. Thus, unlike I²MS, CHARDA requires isotopic resolution
247 for charge state determination.

248

249 **Charge state of individual isotopologues**

250 Close inspection of the CHARDA-predicted z values for individual isotopologues revealed a
251 systematic increase with the isotopologue distance from the monoisotopic peak (see as an
252 example ubiquitin y_{45}^{6+} ion in Figure 4b). To verify this effect, we split the isotopic
253 distributions of the peaks with $z=5+$, $6+$, and $7+$ with similar signal-to-noise ratios into the
254 left and right halves (Figure S2a) and measured the average decay rate for the ion peaks in
255 each half separately. For all three charge states, the right (heavier) parts showed significantly
256 faster decay (Figure S2b). The origin of this effect could be the increased multiplicity of the
257 isotopic fine structure (IFS) for peaks more distant from the monoisotopic one ²⁷. Indeed, a
258 mixture of two close frequencies with equally decaying amplitude gives a pattern with a
259 complex amplitude envelope (Figure 4c), from which the extraction of the original decay
260 constant is nontrivial ²⁸. We calculated the IFS of the 5th isotopic peak of the y_{24} ubiquitin
261 fragment and simulated its transient as a weighted sum of the equally decaying exponents of
262 the individual IFS components (Figure 4d). The TDA of that summed transient gave a 47%
263 larger decay constant than that of each component. As an effective compensation method for
264 this artifact has not been found so far ²⁸, we hypothesized that CHARDA should work best
265 for the molecules with dominant monoisotopic masses.

266 **MS/MS of monoisotopic proteins**

267 Proteins are large molecules, with an average size of bacterial proteins >30 kDa, while the
268 monoisotopic ion peak is usually indiscernible in the noise at MW>10 kDa. Thus to create
269 proteins with abundant monoisotopic ion peaks and test CHARDA applicability on them, we
270 grew *E. coli* bacteria in minimal media with 3-30 fold depleted ²H, ¹³C, ¹⁵N and ¹⁸O isotopes,
271 as well as in normal media for control. At the same amount of protein loaded, LC-MS of the
272 soluble proteome gave 3-5 times more abundant signal for the depleted proteins, as the signal
273 concentrated in fewer isotopic peaks (Figure 5a, S3). This resulted in 283 proteoforms
274 selected for MS/MS in depleted proteome versus 120 proteoforms for normal proteome.
275 Hardklör could not process depleted proteome data in the automatic mode, and had to be
276 supplemented with manual analysis. At least nine proteoforms were identified by MS/MS in
277 both normal and monoisotopic datasets, and 5 proteoforms with 413 monoisotopic peaks in
278 total were used for CHARDA calibration. Consistent with our expectations, CHARDA
279 provided higher resolution (Figure 5b, c), namely R≈5.4 with both TDA and MDI, and 4.5
280 with TDA only for the monoisotopic proteome versus R≈3.2 and 3.4, respectively, for the
281 normal proteome.

282 After calibration, CHARDA could easily identify the charge states of ions for which
283 conventional deconvolution algorithms provided no results. In total, CHARDA identified
284 1120 backbone fragments of 5 proteins and estimated charge states for them in the
285 monoisotopic MS/MS dataset, providing on average 81% sequence coverage (Table S1). Of
286 these, only 321 fragments were identified by Hardklör in the corresponding full-isotope
287 MS/MS dataset, giving on average 41% sequence coverage. The performance of the
288 CHARDA models for the normal (656 peaks) and monoisotopic (413 peaks) MS/MS data are
289 presented in Fig 5b-c, providing R=3.4 for the normal and R=5.4 for the monoisotopic case.

290

291 **Simplified CHARDA**

292 Full-scale CHARDA analysis requires inverse FT of hundreds and thousands of individual
293 peaks, which is calculation-intensive. Thus we tested the simplified CHARDA version
294 (sCHARDA, Figure 6) which compared to the normal FTMS spectrum processing adds to the
295 normal FT procedure only FTs of the two half-transients, maximum doubling the FT
296 calculation time. Yet the charge state resolution obtained with sCHARDA is comparable with
297 that of the full-scale CHARDA (R≈4.0 for ubiquitin 11+ MS/MS spectrum in Figure 3),
298 which is sufficient in many cases.

299

300 **CONCLUSIONS**

301 Here we demonstrated that CHARDA can determine charge states of individual ion peaks in
302 the presence of the isotopic resolution and/or isotopic distribution. CHARDA has no
303 limitation on the lowest charge state unlike other methods ^{7,26} and requires no special
304 acquisition technique except for transient recording. The colour-coding of the ionic charge
305 states resulting from CHARDA provides a 3rd dimension to mass spectra, facilitating
306 analysis of crowded MS and MS/MS data and hinting at possible peak interferences and
307 overlaps. The simplified CHARDA version, sCHARDA, can be implemented in a real-time,
308 online with data acquisition on most FT MS instruments.

309

310 **Acknowledgements**

311 This work was supported by the Swedish Research Council (grants 2017-04303 to RAZ and
312 2020-00687 to AAS), as well as EU Horizon 2020 program (FET OPEN project TopSpec,
313 grant agreement 829157).

314

315 **Author contributions**

316 RAZ has conceived the study and drafted the manuscript; YOT and AM contributed to the
317 concept and implementation; YL implemented CHARDA, created models and software and
318 processed the data, as well as created figures together with AASL; KON and ANK performed
319 transient acquisition and data processing, as well as provided modeling; NG and LM
320 collected LC-MS data, XZ generated monoisotopic samples; ZM provided technical support.
321 All authors critically reviewed the manuscript.

322

323 **Data Availability statement**

324 All the data files underlying the figures are available with CodeOcean computing capsule
325 [DOI identifier will be added upon potential acceptance of the manuscript].

326

327 **Code Availability statement**

328 The source code implementing CHARDA is provided as CodeOcean capsule [submitted
329 directly to Nature Communications Editor for the pee-review process] with no restrictions.
330 The same capsule contains all necessary data and source code for application of CHARDA to
331 form the article figures.

332

333 **Competing interests**

334 The authors declare the absence of competing interests.

335 **Materials & Correspondence**

336 Correspondence and material requests should be addressed to R.A.Z.

337 (Roman.Zubarev@ki.se).

338 **References**

- 339 1. Fenn, J. B., Mann, M., Meng, C. K., Wong, S. F. & Whitehouse, C. M. Electrospray
340 ionization for mass spectrometry of large biomolecules. *Science* (1989)
341 doi:10.1126/science.2675315.
- 342 2. Covey, T. R., Bonner, R. F., Shushan, B. I., Henion, J. & Boyd, R. K. The
343 determination of protein, oligonucleotide and peptide molecular weights by ion-spray
344 mass spectrometry. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* (1988)
345 doi:10.1002/rcm.1290021111.
- 346 3. Horn, D. M., Zubarev, R. A. & McLafferty, F. W. Automated reduction and
347 interpretation of high resolution electrospray mass spectra of large molecules. *J. Am.*
348 *Soc. Mass Spectrom.* (2000) doi:10.1016/S1044-0305(99)00157-9.
- 349 4. Zubarev, R. A., Bitensky, I. S., Demirev, P. A. & Sundqvist, B. U. R. Multiplicities of
350 secondary ions emitted in macromolecular ion impact events. *Nucl. Inst. Methods Phys.*
351 *Res. B* (1994) doi:10.1016/0168-583X(94)96094-1.
- 352 5. Wenzel, R. J., Matter, U., Schultheis, L. & Zenobi, R. Analysis of megadalton ions
353 using cryodetection MALDI time-of-flight mass spectrometry. *Anal. Chem.* (2005)
354 doi:10.1021/ac0482054.
- 355 6. Fuerstenau, S. D. & Benner, W. H. Molecular weight determination of megadalton
356 DNA electrospray ions using charge detection time-of-flight mass spectrometry. *Rapid*
357 *Commun. Mass Spectrom.* (1995) doi:10.1002/rcm.1290091513.
- 358 7. Kafader, J. O. *et al.* Multiplexed mass spectrometry of individual ions improves
359 measurement of proteoforms and their complexes. *Nat. Methods* (2020)
360 doi:10.1038/s41592-020-0764-5.
- 361 8. Wobschall, D., Fluegge, R. A. & Graham, J. R. Collision cross sections of hydrogen
362 and other ions as determined by ion cyclotron resonance. *J. Chem. Phys.* (1967)
363 doi:10.1063/1.1701581.
- 364 9. Yang, F., Voelkel, J. E. & Dearden, D. V. Collision cross sectional areas from analysis
365 of fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance line width: A new method for
366 characterizing molecular structure. *Anal. Chem.* (2012) doi:10.1021/ac300379a.
- 367 10. Sanders, J. D. *et al.* Determination of Collision Cross-Sections of Protein Ions in an
368 Orbitrap Mass Analyzer. *Anal. Chem.* (2018) doi:10.1021/acs.analchem.8b00724.
- 369 11. Bush, M. F. *et al.* Collision cross sections of proteins and their complexes: A
370 calibration framework and database for gas-phase structural biology. *Anal. Chem.*
371 (2010) doi:10.1021/ac1022953.
- 372 12. Kafader, J. O. *et al.* STORI Plots Enable Accurate Tracking of Individual Ion Signals.
373 *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* (2019) doi:10.1007/s13361-019-02309-0.
- 374 13. Mao, L. *et al.* Collision cross section measurements for biomolecules within a high-
375 resolution fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance cell. *Anal. Chem.* (2015)
376 doi:10.1021/acs.analchem.5b00102.
- 377 14. Pomerantz, S. C. & McCloskey, J. A. Fractional mass values of large molecules. *Org.*
378 *mass Spectrom.* **22**, 251–253 (1987).

- 379 15. Mann, M. Useful tables of possible and probable peptide masses. in *PROCEEDINGS*
380 *OF THE ASMS CONFERENCE ON MASS SPECTROMETRY AND ALLIED TOPICS*
381 639 (AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR MASS SPECTROMETRY (ASMS), 1995).
- 382 16. Zubarev, R. A., Håkansson, P. & Sundqvist, B. Accuracy Requirements for Peptide
383 Characterization by Monoisotopic Molecular Mass Measurements. *Anal. Chem.* (1996)
384 doi:10.1021/ac9604651.
- 385 17. Zubarev, R. A. & Bonddarenko, P. V. An A priori relationship between the average
386 and monoisotopic masses of peptides and oligonucleotides. *Rapid Commun. Mass*
387 *Spectrom.* (1991) doi:10.1002/rcm.1290050606.
- 388 18. Zubarev, R. A., Demirev, P. A., Håkansson, P. & Sundqvist, B. U. R. Approaches and
389 Limits for Accurate Mass Characterization of Large Biomolecules. *Anal. Chem.* (1995)
390 doi:10.1021/ac00116a028.
- 391 19. Toumi, M. L. & Desaire, H. Improving mass defect filters for human proteins. *J.*
392 *Proteome Res.* (2010) doi:10.1021/pr100291q.
- 393 20. Bruce, C., Shifman, M. A., Miller, P. & Gulcicek, E. E. Probabilistic enrichment of
394 phosphopeptides by their mass defect. *Anal. Chem.* (2006) doi:10.1021/ac060046w.
- 395 21. Sleno, L. The use of mass defect in modern mass spectrometry. *J. Mass Spectrom.*
396 (2012) doi:10.1002/jms.2953.
- 397 22. Ishitsuka, K., Kakiuchi, T., Sato, H. & Fouquet, T. N. J. An arsenal of tools based on
398 Kendrick mass defects to process congested electrospray ionization high-resolution
399 mass spectra of polymers with multiple charging. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*
400 (2020) doi:10.1002/rcm.8584.
- 401 23. Conrads, T. P., Anderson, G. A., Veenstra, T. D., Paša-Tolić, L. & Smith, R. D. Utility
402 of accurate mass tags for proteome-wide protein identification. *Anal. Chem.* (2000)
403 doi:10.1021/ac0002386.
- 404 24. Nagornov, K. O., Zennegg, M., Kozhinov, A. N., Tsybin, Y. O. & Bleiner, D. Trace-
405 Level Persistent Organic Pollutant Analysis with Gas-Chromatography Orbitrap Mass
406 Spectrometry-Enhanced Performance by Complementary Acquisition and Processing
407 of Time-Domain Data. *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* (2020) doi:10.1021/jasms.9b00032.
- 408 25. Hoopmann, M. R., MacCoss, M. J. & Moritz, R. L. Identification of peptide features in
409 precursor spectra using hardklör and krönik. *Curr. Protoc. Bioinforma.* (2012)
410 doi:10.1002/0471250953.bi1318s37.
- 411 26. Smith, L. M. & Kelleher, N. L. Proteoform: A single term describing protein
412 complexity. *Nature Methods* (2013) doi:10.1038/nmeth.2369.
- 413 27. Yergey, J. A. A general approach to calculating isotopic distributions for mass
414 spectrometry. *Int. J. Mass Spectrom. Ion Phys.* (1983) doi:10.1016/0020-
415 7381(83)85053-0.
- 416 28. Hofmann, A. E. *et al.* Using Orbitrap mass spectrometry to assess the isotopic
417 compositions of individual compounds in mixtures. *Int. J. Mass Spectrom.* (2020)
418 doi:10.1016/j.ijms.2020.116410.

419

420 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

421

422

423

424 **Figure 1.** Charge determination analysis (CHARDA): 1. In transient decay analysis (TDA),
 425 time-domain signal (transient) obtained from an FT mass analyser is converted by FFT to a
 426 frequency spectrum. 2. The latter is converted to an m/z scale spectrum using known ion
 427 peaks or external calibration. 3. Narrow m/z areas around individual peaks are converted to
 428 time-domain transient using inverse FFT. The TDA model is calibrated with parameters of
 429 the transients and charge states of the known ions. 4. Peak-by-peak TDA of the whole mass
 430 spectrum is performed, and for each peak a charge state probability density distribution is
 431 obtained. 5. This distribution is then transferred to mass defect interrogation (MDI). 6. MDI
 432 provides its own charge state probability density distribution. 7. The TDA and MDI charge
 433 state probability density distributions are merged, with the most probable charge state z_0 and
 434 the charge interval $\Delta z_{p<0.05}$ corresponding to $p<0.05$ determined. 8. The peak is labelled with
 435 $z_0 \pm \Delta z_{p<0.05}$ and colour-coded by the CHARDA-estimated charge.

436

437

438

439 **Figure 2. TDA proof of principle.** **a**, The TDA-extracted decay constants of the calibration
 440 ions of ubiquitin 11+ fragments versus their molecular mass. **b**, The distribution of the
 441 CHARDA-predicted charge states of the calibration peaks and their Gaussian fits versus the
 442 charge determined by the deconvolution algorithm (Hardklör).

443

444

445

446 **Figure 3. CHARDA of a busy MS/MS spectrum region.** Charge prediction for individual
 447 ion peaks **(a)**. Subsets of ion peaks with predicted charges $z \leq 4$ **(b)** $3 \leq z \leq 6$ **(c)**, and $z \geq 5$ **(d)**.

448

449

450

451 **Figure 4. CHARDA implementation and features.** **a**, Manual inspection of busy mass
 452 spectra of polypeptide mixtures can be facilitated by CHARDA color coding, with charge
 453 ladders connected by lines for better visibility. CAH – carbonic anhydrase; MYO –
 454 myoglobin; NEO – unidentified protein, possibly a hydrolysis product. **b**, A monotonous
 455 increase of the CHARDA-predicted charge state for high order isotopologues (ion peaks
 456 more distant from the monoisotopic peak). **c**, An interference of two close frequencies with
 457 equally decaying amplitude gives a pattern with a complex amplitude envelope. **d**, The
 458 isotopic distribution of the y_{24} ubiquitin fragment and the calculated isotopic fine structure of
 459 its 5th isotopic peak.

460

461

462

463

464

465

466
467

468 **Figure 5. Comparison of CHARDA performance in top-down analysis of *E. Coli***
 469 **bacteria grown in the normal and isotopically depleted (monoisotopic) media. a,** An
 470 **example of a 6+ molecular ion. b,** Performance of CHARDA (TDA+MDA) models for
 471 **MS/MS fragments of 5 different proteins for the full isotope dataset, R=3.4. c,** The same for
 472 **the monoisotopic dataset, R=5.4.**

473
474
475
476
477
478
479

480

481

482 **Figure 6. A simplified CHARDA (sCHARDA) version.** Compared to the normal FT MS

483 spectrum processing, sCHARDA adds only FTs of the two half-transients to the normal FT

484 procedure, which maximum doubles the FT calculation time.

485

486 **SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS**

487

488 **Table S1.** Comparison of top-down LC-MS/MS analysis of E. Coli proteome with normal
489 isotopic composition (full isotope) and isotopically depleted (monoisotopic).

490

491

Proteoform	Mono-isotopic Mass, Da	Full Isotope spectra			Monoisotopic spectra - CHARDA	
		Clusters	Nr. of fragments	Sequence coverage	Nr. of fragments	Sequence coverage
PFR244733: Cold shock-like protein CspC	7266.72	393	38	39%	199	91%
PFR244781: DNA-binding protein HU-alpha	9529.19	494	75	54%	197	81%
PFR279339: Protein YciI	10595.42	211	24	20%	133	67%
PFR244833: DNA-binding protein HU-beta	9219.99	525	110	54%	295	86%
PFR245160: 50S ribosomal protein L7/L12	12198.48	448	74	40%	296	82%

492

493 **Supplementary Figures**

494

495

496

497 **Figure S1.** The CHARDA (TDA + MDI) model based on ubiquitin 11+ MS/MS data; the
 498 charge resolution is 6.0.

499

500

501

502 **Figure S2. a,** An example of splitting the isotopic distribution of the y_{37}^{6+} ubiquitin ions into
 503 the left and right halves; **b,** decay rate comparison for the left and right halves of the isotopic
 504 distributions of ions with $z=5+$, $6+$ and $7+$. Two-sided Student's t-test for equal variance
 505 samples (Center line, median; box limits contain 50%; upper and lower quartiles, 75 and 25%;
 506 maximum, greatest value excluding outliers; minimum, least value excluding outliers;
 507 outliers, more than 1.5 times of upper and lower quartiles).

508

509

510

511

512

513 **Figure S3.** Comparison of the same part of the MS/MS spectrum of *E. Coli* cold shock-like
 514 protein CspC from (a) the monoisotopic proteome and (b) the normal (full-isotope) proteome.

515

516

517

518

519

520

521